

Order to cash business process enhancement using process mining techniques

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ABSTRACT Over the years, process mining techniques have become more sophisticated, and today they can handle complex processes and large amounts of data. They are used in a wide range of industries, including manufacturing, healthcare, finance, and logistics, to improve efficiency, compliance, and customer satisfaction. Process mining as a field emerged in the late 1990s as a new method for analyzing business processes based on event logs. The goal was to extract knowledge from these logs to understand the actual processes taking place, as opposed to the idealized processes often depicted in process models. Process mining techniques are classified as Discovery: Identify the actual process flow based on event logs. This can reveal deviations from the expected process, bottlenecks, and inefficiencies. Conformance checking: Compare the discovered process with the expected process to identify deviations and non-compliance. Enhancement: Improve the process based on the insights gained from the discovery and conformance-checking stages. This could involve automating certain steps, reassigning resources, or redesigning parts of the process.

Keywords Business process, business process model and notation, conformance checking, directly-follows graph, Order to cash, process discovery, process enhancement, process mining.

I. INTRODUCTION

Process mining is a method of data analysis that allows organizations to improve their business processes. It involves mining data logs from enterprise systems and using that information to identify bottlenecks, inefficiencies, and opportunities for process optimization. In the automotive industry can be a powerful tool for improving efficiency and reducing waste. It can be used to analyze various processes such as manufacturing, supply chain management, sales, and after-sales service. The process of applying process mining can be divided into the following stages. Data Collection: The first step in process mining is to collect event logs from the systems involved in the O2C process. These could include CRM systems, ERP systems, and any other systems that track order management, delivery, invoicing, and payment receipt. Process Discovery: The collected data is then used to create a process model that shows the actual execution of the O2C process. This model can reveal the real workflow, including all variations, and can help identify deviations from the ideal process. Bottleneck Analysis: Process mining tools can be used to analyze the process model for bottlenecks. For example, if there are delays between order receipt and order fulfillment, this could indicate a bottleneck in the order processing stage. Conformance Checking: This involves comparing the discovered process model with the ideal or expected process model. Any deviations can be further investigated to understand their causes. Enhancement: Based on the insights gained, the O2C process can be optimized. This could involve automating certain steps, reassigning resources, or redesigning parts of the process. Monitoring: After implementing changes, process mining can be used for ongoing monitoring to ensure that the improvements are having the desired effect and to identify any new issues that arise.

Process mining in the aftermarket sector can be a valuable tool for understanding and improving various processes such as parts distribution, service scheduling, warranty claims, and customer service. Parts Distribution: Process mining can help identify inefficiencies in the distribution of spare parts. By analyzing event logs from inventory management systems, companies can gain insights into parts usage patterns, lead times, and stock-out incidents. Service Scheduling: Process mining can be used to optimize service scheduling processes.

It can help identify patterns in service requests and optimize scheduling to reduce wait times and improve customer satisfaction. Warranty Claims: Process mining can provide insights into warranty claim processes. It can help identify common reasons for claims, processing times, and potentially fraudulent activity. Customer Service: By analyzing data from customer service systems, process mining can help understand the customer journey, identify common pain points, and improve customer satisfaction.

Process mining in the Order-to-Cash (O2C) process can provide valuable insights into the efficiency and effectiveness of the process. The O2C process is a complex one, involving multiple stages from order receipt, order fulfillment, and invoicing to payment receipt. Each of these stages can be analyzed using process mining techniques to identify bottlenecks, inefficiencies, and opportunities for improvement.

The O2C process can be divided into the following. Order Receipt: Process mining can help identify patterns in order placement, such as peak order times, common order types, and customer preferences. This can help businesses optimize their order intake process. Order Fulfillment: Process mining can analyze the time taken from order receipt to order fulfillment, helping to identify any delays or inefficiencies in the process.

This can assist corporations streamline their order success method and enhance consumer satisfaction. Invoicing: Process mining can help identify any delays or errors in the invoicing process, such as late invoices or incorrect invoice amounts.

This can help businesses improve their invoicing accuracy and efficiency. Payment Receipt: Process mining can analyze the time taken from invoicing to payment receipt, helping to identify any payment delays. This can help businesses improve their cash flow and financial management.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Process mining (PM), a discipline situated at the intersection of data science and process science, aims to extract knowledge from event logs to discover, monitor, and improve business processes [01]. PM supports various phases of the business process management (BPM) lifecycle using data about the execution of a process [02][01]. Relevant research efforts focus on the development and improvement of PM algorithms for different use cases. Initially, PM research centered on control-flow discovery, which involves retrieving a process flow model from an event log. Control-flow discovery remains an important use case [03], but PM research has expanded over time to include techniques for checking conformance between a control-flow model and an event log [04], gaining insights into the involvement of resources in a process [05], and connecting PM to other techniques such as simulation and predictive process monitoring [06][07][08].

Many state-of-the-art PM algorithms have been integrated into the open-source platform ProM, while the use of PM in organizations has been stimulated by the development of commercial tools such as Apromore, Celonis, and Disco [01].

The use of PM in organizations has been extensively studied in both business reports and academic literature. Business reports generally focus on common use cases and vendors based on market assessments. For instance, HSPI has compiled 551 case descriptions [05], while another report [09] highlights PM's role in enhancing transparency in organizations and provides an overview of commercial vendors. Gartner's annual market guide for PM also includes an overview of vendors and common use cases [10]. In addition, Deloitte conducted a survey of early and mature PM adopters to gain insights into PM expectations, critical success factors, application areas, and future deployment plans [11].

In academic literature, two main research streams can be identified regarding the use of PM in organizations. The first is targeted PM case studies that focus on finer granularity, while the second is dedicated research on the general use of PM in organizations at a coarser granularity. Some works concentrate on PM tool comparison and selection [12][13], which are essential for the uptake of PM but focus on the technical aspects of specific techniques or tools and will not be further discussed at the finer granularity level.

Case studies examine how PM techniques are applied in specific organizational contexts, and through detailed analysis of these settings, they provide valuable insights into the opportunities and challenges that arise. For instance, by examining the patient transportation process after traffic accidents in Queensland, [14] found that even advanced PM algorithms struggled to handle its complexity. Additionally, domain expertise was crucial for generating comprehensible results and identifying areas for improvement [14]. Similarly challenging event logs were encountered by researchers studying a telecommunication company's customer fulfillment process; here data integration across multiple systems proved particularly difficult [15]. In compiling twelve case studies from fields such as manufacturing and finance, [16] not only accounted for their impact on each field but also identified key lessons learned- including one point: organizations should use PM to improve future processes rather than blame individuals over past suboptimal performances [16].

Whilst some works report on original case studies, others analyze published ones. These analyses may cover various industries [17][18] or concentrate solely on one such as healthcare [19] or education [20][18]. Having reviewed 144 empirical studies, it is concluded that PM mainly focuses only on a single system within an organization; thus, making cross-system and cross-organizational efforts necessary to aid progress in this area [18]. A similar research approach was taken by those who surveyed 152 cases over time (to study their thoroughness), from which they realized the issue of inadequate problem context consideration during PM projects, hence why more methodological guidance is needed if these problems are being addressed.[17].

Case studies offer valuable insights into the complexities involved in using PM effectively in real-life contexts but tend to be focused firmly upon use-case scenarios pertinent to individual organizations themselves. Conclusions drawn from reviews building off secondary data must likewise reflect its foundations.

Our study serves a distinct purpose compared with pre-existing lines of inquiry: we seek out primary data collected views garnered directly from PM 'experts' possessing widespread practical experience around implementing and utilizing tried-and-tested methods so far - thereby giving us exhaustive understanding related to both opportunities available alongside challenges waiting just beyond current industry discoverable hitherto.

Research dedicated to the general usage of PM in organizations examines a coarser level of granularity. Another area of research, which closely relates to our work, explores organizational mechanisms behind PM use without focusing on specific use cases. Data collection methods such as questionnaires, interviews, or focus groups are used for this purpose.

Lately, there have been two studies focused on how organizations implement and utilize PM. The first one [21] centers on a Dutch pension fund that recently incorporated a commercial PM tool into its operations. This study identified seven obstacles and four facilitators for successful implementation through nine stakeholder interviews conducted by the researchers. Among the challenges are insufficient governance mechanisms, lack of coordination between designers and end-users, as well as issues with data quality. Conversely, some enablers include being able to generate effective insights from using PM tools; having confidence in results; observing benefits upon adoption of these methods; and having access to proper training in applying them accurately [21].

While some studies focus on a single organization's implementation of PM, others take a broader perspective by incorporating the insights from multiple process managers. For instance, in their report based on a focus group consisting of 22 operations experts across Switzerland, Germany, and Liechtenstein [22], key findings include the challenging but possible ability to create business

value through PM (which is difficult to quantify), difficulties in selecting appropriate processes for using project management tools/methods effectively as well as gathering requisite data being non-trivial tasks. Moreover, implementing effective use of such methods requires adjusting/navigating increased transparency which could be related to unintended consequences if not managed properly. Lastly organizations must ensure alignment between strategic goals/operations and initiatives thus implemented before any plans sparked up from these discussions.

The authors acknowledge limitations due to limited geographic spread/expertise covered during this study's momentary dependence upon those present for responses yet stress the need for more comprehensive/targeted explorations into organizational adoption patterns or otherwise utilization preference towards adopting various Process Mining paradigms.[21]

A crucial link between data mining and business process modeling is process mining. Having access to the event logs of business applications is essential to using process mining. It is frequently implemented as a component of multiple applications, therefore obtaining all the IT tools required for this procedure and combining the dispersed data [23]

New directions in business process management include inspecting process variability and configuration, the quality of process models, and process mining methods (i.e., automatic detection, compliance checking, performance search, extraction of variants and variants, operational support) [24]

III.METHODOLOGY AND IMPLEMENTATION

Since Toyota Egypt group has implemented SAP ERP with industry-specific for automotive with green field implementation migrated from inhouse application based on the AS400 platform, the selected solution is SAP S4Hana with vehicle sales and service modules. Implementing Order-to-Cash (O2C) process mining involves a systematic methodology to ensure successful discovery, analysis, and optimization of the order fulfillment process.

The Objective is to extract log data from the ERP system and focus on the order to cash process implemented, thus comparing all actions and process flow that happened in February vs September 2023 to show all process enhancements. For data collection We have used the database file VLCHISTORY which contains actions implemented on vehicles for procurement, sales, and service from Sap S4Hana ERP, as shown in Table 1, knowing that, internal vehicle number will represent Case ID, action control, and primary status is used for procure to pay (P2P) business process which is not in our scope, however, action control and secondary status will be used to Order to Cash O2C business process.

TABLE 1
SAP DATABASE FILE STRUCTURE

Table Name: VLCHISTORY	
VHICLE	Internal Vehicle Number
MMCTR	Action Control
MMSTA	Primary Status
SDCTR	Action Control
SDSTA	Secondary Status
MMTSP	Time Stamp
ERNAM	Name of the Person who Created the Object

Data Preprocessing: Extracted log file for two months February 2023 and September 2023. The file contains vehicle sales and service business process, and vehicle management system, order to cash/procure to pay business process as shown in table 2.

TABLE 2
Log Summary

	Case Count	Action	Event
February 2023	181,034	71	548,077
September 2023	311,801	71	828,036

We have divided the table to select only transactions related to vehicles with the process of Vehicle Management System (VMS) and dropped other transactions related to Vehicle the Sales and Services (VSS) process as shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3
Log Summary - Module

Month	Module	Case Count	Action	Event	Status
Feb-23	VMS	5,329	58	16,064	Selected
	VSS	176,777	15	532,013	Dropped
Sep-23	VMS	4,544	57	21,371	Selected
	VSS	307,936	15	806,665	Dropped

Also, we did a split to select only transactions related to the Order to Cash (O2C) business process as shown in Table 4

TABLE 4
Log Summary – E2E Process

Month	Module	Case Count	Action	Event	Case Count
Feb-23	VMS	5,329	58	16,064	Total
	VMS-O2C	1,632	24	5,517	Selected
	VMS-P2P	4,714	35	11,076	Dropped
Sep-23	VMS	4,544	57	21,371	Total
	VMS-O2C	1,596	21	4,038	Selected
	VMS-P2P	4,015	37	16,597	Dropped

IV.RESULTS

A. Log Summary

The O2C process of vehicle streamline “Create sales order” > “create outbound delivery” > “post goods issue” > “create billing document” > “actual delivery”. However, the O2C process of material handling “Create sales order” > “create outbound delivery” > “create goods issue” > “create outgoing invoice” > “actual delivery”. Thus, we have selected for February 2023 the Start activity = create sales order (Selected cases is 561) and Select end activity = create actual delivery (selected final cases = 129). For September 2023 Selected Start activity = create sales order (Selected cases = 332) and Selected end activity = create actual delivery (Selected final cases = 95) and for both months we have removed all returns and cancelations.

Activity occurrence: - Action “Actual Deliver” has the most repeated actions (181 cases) and this is due to the migration of the old system to the new system without completing the cycle, with the case of sold and not delivered as shown in figure 1, however in figure 2 the process has been completed in sequence with creating sales order (99 case) and actual deliver (93). Outbound delivery and create billing documents have the same number of repeating (74 cases)

Figure 1
Log Summary - Activity Occurrences – February 2023

Figure 2
Log Summary - Activity Occurrences September 2023

Bottlenecks analysis: - shows that there is a huge waiting time for the actual delivery of both periods February and September 2023, and this is due to the nature of sales in the free zone area in Egypt which takes a lot of time to complete the process as shown in figure 3 and figure 4.

Figure 3
Log Summary – Bottlenecks - February 2023

predecessor	successor	# occurrences	duration ↓
Create Outgoing Invoice	Actual Delivery	33	4w 12h 14m 50s
Create Billing Document	Actual Delivery	88	1w 4d 15h 20m 27s
Create Outgoing Invoice	Status Correction (Without Check)	8	1w 5h 19m 22s
Create Sales Order	Create Goods Issue	40	4d 17h 29m 30s
Create Outbound Delivery	Create Goods Issue	15	2d 4h 39m 24s
Status Correction (Without Check)	Actual Delivery	9	1d 14h 11m 26s
Create Sales Order	Create Outbound Delivery	81	19h 47m 47s

Figure 4
Log Summary – Bottlenecks - September 2023

predecessor	successor	# occurrences	duration ↓
Create Billing Document	Actual Delivery	74	5mo 1w 9h 47m 9s
Create Sales Order	Delete Fixed Link	7	2mo 4d 12h 41m 47s
Create Outgoing Invoice	Actual Delivery	18	1mo 1w 3d 14h 20m 26s
Create Sales Order	Create delivery	18	2w 4d 17h 9m 37s
Create Sales Order	Create Outbound Delivery	74	1h 38m 3s
Delete Fixed Link	Create Sales Order	7	44m 26s
Create Outbound Delivery	Post Goods Issue	34	28m 41s

Variant explorer analysis: - figure 5 shows that there are some cases with has "Create Goods Issue" action before the "Create Outbound Delivery" action in February as this behavior is not accepted and has been fixed as shown in Figure 6

Figure 5
Log Summary - Variant Explorer - February 2023

Figure 6
Log Summary - Variant Explorer - September 2023

B. Process Discovery

Directly-flows graph (DFG): - as shown in figure 7 and 8, comparing the process activity in February and September process mining discovery shows that the action "status correction (without check)" has not been used due to the process came into more stable status without forcing in status changes as each action is linked to status changes before and after with authorization to a specific user role. The action creates goods issue was fixed in September and became after creating outbound delivery instead of creating a sales order.

Figure 7
DFG February 2023

Figure 8
DFG September 2023

Business Process Model Notation (BPMN):- as shown in Figure 9 for February the next check after activity "Create Sales Order " has AND condition to "create deliver" or "Create Outbound Delivery" in parallel with "Create Goods Issue" also action "status correction (without check)" has been used which causes to unstable process flow. However, in Figure 10 for September the only sequential process activity is "Post Goods Issue" and "Create Goods Issue" due to the process came into more stable status without forcing status changes as each action is linked to status changes before and after with authorization to a specific user role.

Figure 9
BPMN February 2023

Figure 10
BPMN September 2023

V. CONCLUSION

Through the application of process mining techniques, Toyota Egypt group successfully optimized its Order-to-Cash process, leading to improved efficiency, enhanced visibility, and cost savings. The insights gained from process mining enabled data-driven decision-making and laid the foundation for continuous process improvement.

This case study serves as an example framework and can be tailored to match the specific context, challenges, and objectives by applying the below as an example: -

Supply Chain Optimization: Analyzing the supply chain using process mining can help identify bottlenecks, delays, and inefficiencies. By visualizing the end-to-end supply chain processes, automotive companies can optimize inventory levels, reduce lead times, and enhance overall supply chain performance.

Predictive Maintenance: Analyzing maintenance processes using process mining can lead to predictive maintenance strategies. By monitoring equipment and machinery data, automotive companies can predict when maintenance is needed, reducing downtime, and extending the lifespan of critical assets.

Customer Relationship Management (CRM): Process mining can be used to analyze customer interactions, sales processes, and after-sales services. By understanding the customer journey, automotive companies can improve customer satisfaction, personalize services, and optimize sales processes.

Logistics and Distribution: Process mining aids in optimizing logistics and distribution processes by visualizing the flow of goods, identifying delays, and optimizing routes. This can lead to cost reductions, improved delivery times, and enhanced overall logistics efficiency.

Warranty and Recall Management: Analyzing warranty and recall processes using process mining can help identify patterns related to product issues, warranty claims, and recall procedures. This can streamline the handling of warranty claims, reduce recall response times, and minimize the impact on customers.

Finance and Procurement Processes: Finance and procurement processes can benefit from process mining to optimize invoicing, payment processes, and procurement workflows. Identifying inefficiencies in these processes can lead to cost savings and improved financial management.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to acknowledge MEAPAL Data Science @ CORELIA <https://www.corelia.ai/> for their wonderful collaboration and support and for all of the opportunities given to further research.

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